

Studies in Galvanoluminescence : Part II. Chemical Effects of Cathode Glow

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When ordinary electrolysis is carried out at an applied voltage much higher than the decomposition potential, following an incubation period a spontaneous transition to a new type of electrolysis (called galvanoluminescence) accompanied by appearance of luminescence at an electrode preferentially at the cathode, occurs. The chemical effects of cathode glow process have been investigated. The chemical results of cathode glow remarkably differ from those by conventional electrolysis in that the yield is in excess of the Faraday law value and that the gas liberated at the glowing cathode is a liberal mixture of hydrogen and oxygen. Further depending upon the nature of electrolyte other unconventional products may be obtained. Effects of variables like voltage, current, area and intensity of luminosity and nature of glow condition on the degree of these non-Faradaic features have been studied. A critical analysis of the chemical results produced by cathode glow in a variety of aqueous electrolytes has been made. The results have been shown to be partly Faradaic and partly non-Faradaic. An interpretation based on energy transfer and charge transfer mechanisms has been offered.

WHEN conventional electrolysis is carried out at an applied voltage sufficiently higher than the decomposition potential, following an incubation period, a dramatic switch-over to a radically different phenomenon marked by a sudden drop in the ammeter reading with simultaneous appearance of luminosity at one of the electrodes, occurs spontaneously. The new phenomenon called 'galvanoluminescence' or 'glow-electrolysis' characterised by several other interesting features is of quite general occurrence and easily produced in a variety of electrolytes only if the voltage input is suitably high¹. It is to be pointed out that though the luminescence can be made to appear either at the cathode, or at the anode by suitably adjusting the experimental conditions, there is in general a much stronger preference for the glow to appear at the cathode than at the anode.

Highly interesting are the chemical changes brought about by galvanoluminescence. The chemical effects thus produced differ remarkably from those by conventional electrolysis in that the yield obtained is in excess of the value stipulated by Faraday's law and that unconventional products are usually formed. Thus during anodic glow-electrolysis Hickling and associates² found H_2O_2 from aqueous inert systems and N_2H_4 from liquid ammonia systems in yields greater than 1 equiv./F. That the chemical yield of cathodic glow-electrolysis is in far excess of the Faraday law value was first reported by Palit³ who further demonstrated that the gas liberated at the luminescent cathode contains a considerable amount of oxygen. The present investigation was undertaken to make a comprehensive study of the chemical effects with particular emphasis on the aspect of co-liberation of hydrogen and oxygen at the luminescent

cathode produced by cathode glow process in a variety of aqueous electrolytes under different conditions. A critical analysis of the results thus obtained is reported in this paper.

Experimental

The electrolysis was carried out in a U-type Pyrex cell (Fig. 1) provided with two gas outlets one or both of which could be connected through a system of gas burettes to a Hempel type oxygen analyzer where oxygen content in the sample gas was estimated by absorption in alkaline pyrogallol. Hydrogen was estimated by explosion method and this was done in a separate unit. The following standard conditions were generally used : electrolyte, 0.2-0.3N solution; electrodes, platinum wire; diameter of cathode, 0.35 mm; length of cathode, 6-8 mm; the anode used was more or less of identical dimensions or larger than the cathode in suitable cases; the distance of each of the electrodes below the free surface of electrolyte, 4-5 cm; voltage applied between the electrodes was usually ~ 210 volts D.C. current was supplied from a number of accumulators connected in series to give a voltage upto 260 volts. Current was passed to the cell through an ammeter and the voltage across the cell was read on a voltmeter. During the period when yields of chemical products of cathode glow were studied owing to local fluctuation in the glow region the current strength varied within ± 10 mA. To measure the total quantity of electricity passed and to compute the average current strength during glow process, a Lingane-type gas coulometer fitted with suitably large platinum electrodes and containing 0.5M K_2SO_4 solution was included in the circuit.

Fig. 1.—(A—Ammeter; V—Voltmeter; C—Lingane-type Gas Coulometer).

Chemical Results of Cathode Luminescence

The chemical effects produced by cathode glow have been found to be remarkably different from those by conventional electrolysis. Two most noteworthy features are :

(1) The volume of gas liberated at the luminescent cathode is much greater than what could be predicted from Faraday's law i.e., there is a positive deviation from Faraday's law.

(2) The gas liberated at the glowing cathode is always a liberal mixture of hydrogen and oxygen.

Besides depending upon the nature of electrolyte used, many other unconventional products may be obtained.

In the following is presented an account of the results obtained during cathode glow in various types of aqueous electrolytes.

(a) *Inert type sodium, potassium and barium salts and alkalis as electrolytes* : The gas volume liberated at the glowing cathode is in substantial excess (from 130% to 370%) of the Faraday law value and the cathode gas contains considerable percentage (from 8–22%) of oxygen (vide Table 1.1). From the table it is seen that more positive the deviation from Faraday's law, higher is the proportion of oxygen in the cathode gas and that the non-Faradaic behaviour is more strongly manifested with alkalis and salts of strong acids rather than with salts of weak acids. As a result of cathode glow, no new species are however produced in the catholyte in

quantities sufficient for qualitative detection. In fact, if one allows for decomposition of water molecules into hydrogen and oxygen in addition to usual Faradaic reduction of H_3O^+ or H_2O to H_2 a material balance can be achieved within the limits of experimental error.

TABLE 1.1.—CHEMICAL RESULTS OF CATHODE GLOW WITH INERT TYPE ELECTROLYTES

Electrolyte	Concentration	Voltage applied (volts) D.C.	Average current strength during glow (mA)	V_C/V_{FC} %	V_{O_2}/V_C %
$KHSO_4$	0.2(N)	220	206	175.5	15.1
K_2SO_4	0.2(N)	216	129	258	20.4
Na_2SO_4	0.3(N)	220	157	222	18.3
NaH_2PO_4	0.4(N)	220	186	209	17.4
Na_2HPO_4	0.4(N)	214	105	260	20.0
KCl	0.2(N)	216	200	201	17.1
NaCl	0.2(N)	216	155	214	17.7
$BaCl_2$	0.2(N)	212	198	310	22.6
$NaHCO_3$	0.3(N)	216	114	148	10.9
Na_2CO_3	0.3(N)	216	120	143	10.0
$Na_2B_4O_7$	0.4(N)	216	80	134	8.5
KOH	0.2(N)	216	175	209	17.4
NaOH	0.2(N)	220	220	239	19.3

The meaning of the symbol given in the tables (1.1–1.4) of the paper viz. V_C , V_{FC} and V_{O_2} is as follows.

V_C —Volume of the cathode gas liberated after being washed by acid or alkali or by both (depending upon the nature of the gas produced). V_C is usually composed of H_2 and O_2 . N_2 may be present in suitable cases.

V_{FC} —Volume of the cathode gas that would have been obtained for the given quantity of electricity according to Faraday's law. This is calculated as 2/3rd of the total gas volume liberated in a Lingane coulometer put in series with the experimental cell. Further, V_{FC} is the volume of hydrogen that would be liberated for the given quantity of electricity under normal electrolytic condition. This is practically true for almost all the electrolytes used excepting nitrites nitrates and nitric acid.

V_{O_2} —Volume of O_2 found in V_C .

(b) *Sodium, potassium, barium and strontium salts with reducible anions as electrolytes* : During cathode glow with such salts, the magnitude of deviation from Faraday law value (the latter being always calculated on the basis of reduction of H_2O^+ or H_3O to H_2 only) although does not appreciably differ from that with inert electrolytes, the extent of co-liberation in the cathode gas is usually substantially higher in the former case. The reason for the higher percentage of oxygen resulting from cathode glow with such

salts appears to be two-fold : (1) Competition of the oxidising anions with H_3O^+ or H_2O in Faradaic reduction lowering the yield of hydrogen thereby; and (2) thermal decomposition of the salts themselves giving more oxygen. In fact during cathode glow, NH_4^+ from nitrites, NH_4^+ and NO_2^- from nitrates, Cl^- from perchlorates, $SO_4^{=}$ from persulphates, Cr^{+3} from chromates and dichromates, and Mn^{+4} from permanganates can be detected in the corresponding catholyte solutions. It may be noted that greater the tendency of a salt to undergo thermal decomposition to give O_2 , higher is the percentage of oxygen in the cathode gas with that salt. Thus, compared to other such salts chromates give a somewhat lower percentage of oxygen whereas persulphates give rather a much higher percentage of oxygen (vide Table 1.2).

TABLE 1.2-- CHEMICAL RESULTS OF CATHODE GLOW WITH ELECTROLYTES HAVING OXIDISING ANIONS

Electrolyte	Concentration	Voltage applied (volts) D.C.	Average current strength during glow (mA)	V_c/V_{FC} %	V_{O_2}/V_c %
$NaNO_2$	0.2(N)	220	140	196	20.0
$NaNO_3$	0.2(N)	220	140	172	28.6
KNO_3	0.2(N)	224	182	238	31.8
$Mg(NO_3)_2$	0.2(N)	220	50	270	26.0
$Ba(NO_3)_2$	0.3(N)	216	170	264	28.0
$Sr(NO_3)_2$	0.2(N)	216	166	343	28.0
$KClO_4$	0.13(N)	224	166	284	25.8
$K_2S_2O_8$	0.2(N)	220	165	235	45.2
K_2CrO_4	0.2(N)	212	203	263	24.6
$K_2Cr_2O_7$	0.2(N)	212	213	283	26.0
$KMnO_4$	0.2(N)	240	180	264	28.5

(c) *Inorganic acids as electrolytes: HCl, HNO₃, HClO₄, H₂SO₄ and H₃PO₄*: The results with acids are more interesting (vide Table 1.3) and each individual acid gives products characteristic of its own. From an analysis of the products obtained it appears that apart from usual Faradaic reduction of H_3O^+ to hydrogen and breakup of water molecules into H_2 and O_2 , considerable decomposition of the acids themselves and competition of the reducible anions, if present, with H_3O^+ in Faradaic reduction, take place. Further some acids e.g., HCl, HNO₃ and HClO₄ give remarkably different results depending upon the type of glow condition developed (vide Table 1.3).

When hydrochloric acid solutions are subjected to galvanoluminescence, H_2 , O_2 and some Cl_2 get liberated in the cathode gas space and the catholyte strongly responds to starch-iodide test. The latter

appears to be due to dissolved chlorine or some oxide of chlorine like ClO_2 or some oxyacid of chlorine like HOCl, $HClO_2$, $HClO_3$ or all of them. From a closer examination of the results it seems that under glow condition besides water some HCl molecules get dissociated to H_2 and Cl_2 and the latter partly dissolves in the catholyte. Further, some chlorine atoms or molecules produced in the glowing section may react with oxygen (from H_2O dissociation) to give oxides of chlorine like Cl_2O , ClO_2 etc. and these like Cl_2 dissolve in the catholyte where they react to give oxyacids of chlorine such as HOCl, $HClO_2$, $HClO_3$ etc. Oxyacids such as HOCl, $HClO_2$ and anions of oxyacid such as ClO_3^- may subsequently compete with H_3O^+ in Faradaic reduction. The effectiveness with which these species compete with H_3O^+ depends upon the glow-condition produced. With HCl solutions at least two types of glow characterised by their colour can be produced. One is blue and the other is pink in colour. The rate of gas liberation under the former condition is visibly much greater than under the latter one. When the cathode glow is blue in colour, there is positive deviation from Faraday's law and the percentage of oxygen in the cathode gas is not too high (~10%), whereas when the glow is pink in colour, there may occur an apparent negative deviation from Faraday's law but the percentage of oxygen in the cathode gas may be considerably high (~18%) (vide Table 1.3). The remarkable difference in results produced

TABLE 1.3—CHEMICAL RESULTS OF CATHODE GLOW WITH INORGANIC ACIDS AS ELECTROLYTES

Electrolyte	Voltage applied (volts) D.C.	Average current strength during glow (mA)	Colour of the cathode glow produced	V_c/V_{FC} %	V_{O_2}/V_c %
HCl (0.6N)	200	93.8	Blue	115	10.1
HCl (0.6N)	180	131	Pink	83	18.6
HNO ₃ (0.6N)	216	125	Blue	370	31.1
HNO ₃ (0.6N)	216	130	Pink	32.6	35.7
HClO ₄ (0.6N)	180	70	Blue	193	20.4
HClO ₄ (0.6N)	200	100	Pink	77.8	91.9
HClO ₄ (0.6N)	180	46	Intermediate between blue and pink	118	88.5
H ₂ SO ₄ (0.6N)	220	74.5	Blue	192	18.8
H ₃ PO ₄ (4.5N)	240	75	Blue	230	17.5

under different glow conditions appears to be connected with the efficiency of the oxyacid species (HOCl, $HClO_2$, ClO_3^-) in cathodic reduction. It is apparent that this efficiency is much greater with pink glow rather than with blue glow and that with the former type of glow these species become so much efficient that they predominate over H_3O^+ in Faradaic

reduction giving an apparent negative deviation from Faraday's law.-

Results from nitric acid solutions are qualitatively similar to those from nitrate solutions if the glow produced is blue in colour (vide Table 1.3). As with HCl solutions, another type of glow pink in colour can also be developed in HNO₃ solutions. With such pink glow in HNO₃ solutions, there again occurs apparent large negative deviation from Faraday's law (vide Table 1.3). The difference in the chemical effects of two types of glow under otherwise more or less similar conditions is so much that the ratio V_c/V_{Fc} in blue glow condition is more than 11 times that in pink glow condition. This appears to arise principally from much greater efficiency of NO₃⁻ over H₃O⁺ in Faradaic reduction under our pink glow condition. With both types of glow it is likely that some acid molecules along with water molecules get decomposed.

With perchloric acid solutions also two types of glow, one pink and other blue in colour can be produced. With blue glow as in the previous cases there usually occurs a positive deviation from Faraday's law (vide Table 1.3) and the percentage of oxygen in the cathode gas during such glow in HClO₄ may be sufficiently high (~20%). In other words under blue glow condition results of HClO₄ are qualitatively similar to those with perchlorate solutions. However, the results with perchloric acid solution under pink glow condition are highly remarkable in the sense that apart from the apparent negative deviation from Faraday's law, the percentage of oxygen in the gas liberated at the glowing cathode is abnormally high, over 90% (vide Table 1.3). It appears that ClO₄⁻ greatly predominates over H₃O⁺ in Faradaic reduction and that HClO₄ molecules (which give O₂ on decomposition) are decomposed to a greater extent than H₂O molecules, under such pink glow condition. These two causes can well account for such low percentage of hydrogen occurring in the cathode gas observed under this glow condition. As expected Cl⁻ can be detected in the catholyte with both types of glow. Moreover, oxides of chlorine like ClO₂ produced on decomposition of HClO₄ may dissolve in the catholyte and react there to give oxyacids like HClO₃. Such oxyacids or their anions may subsequently take part in cathodic reduction.

Apart from these two types of glow other forms of glow having colour intermediate between blue and pink can also be developed and the results under such intermediate conditions are also intermediate in nature. Thus with HClO₄ solutions under such an intermediate glow condition there occurs some positive deviation from Faraday's law (V_c/V_{Fc} ~120%) and the proportion of oxygen in the cathode gas is at the same time unusually high, over 80% (vide Table 1.3).

Results with sulphuric and phosphoric acid solutions are much less complex than those with HCl, HNO₃ and HClO₄ solutions. With these two acids only one type of glow, the blue coloured one is usually produced and there generally occurs positive

deviation from Faraday's law as well as substantial percentage of oxygen in the cathode gas (vide Table 1.3). With H₂SO₄ solutions, the percentage of oxygen in the cathode gas is higher than that expected on the basis of decomposition of water into H₂ and O₂ concurrent with Faradaic reduction of only H₃O⁺ ions to H₂. This higher oxygen content probably arises from decomposition of H₂SO₄ molecules into O₂ and SO₂. The latter can be detected in the cathode gas as well as in the catholyte. Results from H₃PO₄ solutions are still less complex and similar to those from inert type electrolytes. However, during cathode glow in H₃PO₄, the catholyte gives positive test for hydrogen peroxide and also the oxygen content in the cathode gas is lower than that expected on the basis of breakup of H₂O into H₂ and O₂ with simultaneous reduction of H₃O⁺ to H₂. This lower oxygen content is evidently due to H₂O₂ formed in the catholyte. It is also evident that H₃PO₄ molecules are sufficiently stable not to undergo any decomposition at least under our glow condition. Considering Faradaic reduction of H₃O⁺ to H₂, breakup of water molecules into H₂ and O₂ with simultaneous formation of H₂O₂, material balance can be achieved.

(d) *Ammonium salts as electrolytes*: From Table 1.4 it is seen that during cathode glow with (NH₄)₂SO₄ and NH₄Cl solutions although the deviation from Faraday law value is substantially larger, the proportion of oxygen in the cathode gas is considerably lower than the respective figures with analogous alkali metal salts. Calculation shows that the cathode gas volume is much greater than that could be accounted for by simple cathodic reduction of H₃O⁺ to H₂ and dissociation of H₂O into H₂ and O₂. On electrolysis the catholyte becomes alkaline and gives off ammonia which probably breaks up into N₂ and H₂ under glow condition. In fact, analysis shows that nitrogen is present in the cathode gas in significant proportion (~13%). The dissociation of NH₃ into N₂ and H₂ can well account for the

TABLE 1.4—CHEMICAL RESULTS OF CATHODE GLOW WITH AMMONIUM SALTS AS ELECTROLYTES

Electrolyte	Concentration	Voltage applied (volts) D.C.	Average current strength during glow (mA)	V_c/V_{Fc} %	V_{O_2}/V_c %
NH ₄ Cl	0.6(N)	220	1.15	400%	4.5%
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	0.9(N)	228	97.5	297%	5.4%

It is to be noted that this V_c contains sufficient N₂ in addition to H₂ and O₂. Percentage of N₂ found in V_c was 15.2% with NH₄Cl and 12% with (NH₄)₂SO₄; and that of H₂ was 80.3% with NH₄Cl and 82.6% with (NH₄)₂SO₄.

larger volume of cathode gas and the lower percentage of oxygen as well. Another interesting aspect is the formation of NO₂⁻ in the catholyte. This probably

arises from dissolution of a mixture of NO and NO₂ in the alkaline catholyte, the mixture being produced by oxidation of ammonia by O₂ (from water dissociation) under glow condition. Further, catholyte from ammonium sulphate gives positive test for SO₃ = i.e., dissolved SO₂. The latter appears to arise from the thermal decomposition of the salt itself.

The results cited in the above tables are representative figures only. From a quite good number of experimental recordings it has been found that the average current strength varies over a 10 mA range for a particular glow when variation of the ratio V_c/V_{Fc} is within 7% and that of the ratio VO_2/V_c is within 3.5%.

We thus see that the nature of chemical results produced by cathode luminescence differs remarkably from that by ordinary electrolysis. Furthermore the different electrolytes used, almost all of which are known to give identical products (i.e., H₂) at the cathode under ordinary electrolysis, give significantly different products at the cathode under glow condition. However, during cathode glow, the chemical effects produced at the anode are identical to those produced under ordinary electrolytic condition.

Effect of some important variables on non-Faradaic aspects of Galvanoluminescence

The deviation from Faraday's law and co-liberation in the cathode gas are common features of cathode glow process and depending upon the nature of the electrolyte used other novel features may be developed. However, from preliminary studies it has been observed that the degree of the two principal non-Faradaic aspects viz., magnitude of the positive deviation from Faraday's law and the extent of co-liberation in the cathode gas is affected substantially by a number of factors among which the important are voltage input, current strength, area of glow, intensity of luminosity and the nature of the glow condition produced.

To see how the degree of the non-Faradaic features is modulated by these factors, necessary experiments on chemical effects of cathode glow were carried out. To have least complication in such studies, we used some suitable inert electrolytes such as sodium or potassium sulphate solutions and the results obtained are described below :

(a) *Effect of voltage input* : To study the effect of voltage, cathode gases liberated during cathode glow produced at different voltages with suitably

TABLE 2.1—EFFECT OF VOLTAGE INPUT ON NON-FARADAIC ASPECTS OF CATHODE GLOW

Electrolyte	Voltage input (volts) D.C.	Average current during glow (mA)	V_c/V_{Fc} %	VO_2/V_c %
Na ₂ SO ₄ (0.4N)	188	174	207	17.2
Na ₂ SO ₄ (0.4N)	212	174	216	18.0

concentrated Na₂SO₄ solution at the same glow current, were analyzed and the results obtained are

given in Table 2.1. From the table it is seen that higher the voltage input greater is the deviation from Faraday law value and more is the percentage of oxygen in the cathode gas.

(b) *Effect of current strength* : To study this effect, cathode gases liberated during cathode glow produced at different glow current values but at the same voltage with suitably concentrated Na₂SO₄ solutions, were analyzed and the results are given in Table 2.2.

TABLE 2.2—EFFECT OF CURRENT STRENGTH ON NON-FARADAIC ASPECTS OF CATHODE GLOW

Electrolyte	Voltage applied (volts) D.C.	Average current strength during glow (mA)	V_c/V_{Fc} %	VO_2/V_c %
Na ₂ SO ₄ (0.6N)	212	210	255	20.2
Na ₂ SO ₄ (0.8N)	212	255	322	23.1

From the table it is seen that higher the current strength, stronger is the departure from Faraday law value and higher is the proportion of oxygen in the cathode gas.

(c) *Effect of area of luminosity* : Since cathode glow usually spreads over whole area of the electrode, increase of area of luminosity can be achieved by using cathodes of increasing surface area. Hence

TABLE 2.3—EFFECT OF AREA OF LUMINOSITY ON NON-FARADAIC ASPECTS OF CATHODE GLOW

Electrolyte—1.0(N) Na₂SO₄ solution.
Electrodes :

Anode—A rectangular Pt foil (9.5 mm × 10 mm) of thickness 0.05 mm in all cases.

Cathode—Either Pt wires of dia. 0.35 mm or rectangular Pt foils of thickness 0.05 mm. Further details of the cathode size are mentioned below.

Cathode used	Surface area of cathode (mm ²)	Voltage input (volts) D.C.	Average current during glow (mA)	V_c/V_{Fc} %	VO_2/V_c %
4 mm long Pt wire.	~ 4.5	224	200	188	15.6
9 mm long Pt wire	~ 10.0	224	270	280	21.3
13 mm long Pt wire.	~ 14.4	224	280	373	24.4
(5 mm × 4 mm) Pt foil	~ 40.7	224	310	427	25.7

It is to be noted that with concentrated solutions like 1.0(N) Na₂SO₄ different types of glow conditions can be developed at a cathode and chemical results of such different glow conditions are remarkably different (vide 'Nature of glow condition and its effect' and Table 2.5) and that the trend shown in Table 2.3 may not be observed unless the glow conditions produced at different sized cathodes are of the same type.

to study the influence of this factor cathode gases liberated during galvanoluminescence produced at cathodes of varying sizes and shapes (such as wire and sheet) in 1*N* Na₂SO₄ solutions under otherwise same conditions, were analyzed and the results are given in Table 2.3. From the table it is seen that greater the surface area of a cathode irrespective of its shape, hence larger the area of luminosity greater is the deviation from Faraday law value and more extensive is the co-liberation of oxygen and hydrogen in the cathode gas. However, increase of glowing area automatically necessitates higher glow current at the same voltage and higher power consumption.

(d) *Effect of intensity of luminosity*: By varying the voltage input, the intensity of cathode glow can be altered and with increase of voltage the intensity of luminosity increases. Further the glow current for stronger glow is also higher. Hence, to study the influence of this factor, cathode gases liberated during cathode glow produced at different voltages with 0.5*N* K₂SO₄ solutions under otherwise same conditions were analyzed and the results are presented in Table 2.4. From the table it is seen that higher the

TABLE 2.4—EFFECT OF INTENSITY OF LUMINOSITY ON NON-FARADAIC ASPECTS OF CATHODE GLOW

Electrolyte—0.5(*N*) K₂SO₄ solution.
Electrodes:

Anode—15 mm long Pt wire of dia. 0.35 mm in all cases.
Cathode—4 mm long Pt wire of dia. 0.35 mm in all cases.

Voltage applied (volts) D.C.	Average current during glow (mA)	Colour of glow produced	V_c/V_{FC} %	V_{O_2}/V_c %
96	72	No visible glow i.e., non-glow condition	110	3.0
132	166	Faint violet glow	125	6.7
168	188	Violet glow	149	10.8
204	228	Violet glow	202	16.8
240	245	Red violet glow	233	19.3

voltage input hence higher the intensity of luminosity, greater is the departure from Faraday law value and more extensive is the co-liberation in cathode gas. The table also gives results obtained under non-glow condition. The latter develops when the voltage applied is sufficient for the breakdown of normal electrolysis (indicated by a steep drop in the ammeter reading) but not high enough for the emission of visible luminescence from the vapour mantle formed around the cathode. As can be seen from the table that under this condition both positive deviation from Faraday's law and co-liberation still occur but only to a small extent.

(e) *Nature of glow condition and its effect*: It has been already pointed out how remarkably the yield

and the nature of chemical effects of cathode glow with acids like HCl, HNO₃ and HClO₄ are oriented by the nature of glow condition developed. Even with simple inert type electrolytes e.g., Na₂SO₄ under suitable conditions different types of glow occurring at different glow currents can be developed at the same applied voltage and with the same solution in the same cell set-up. Among these at least two types can be clearly distinguished from direct observation and the others may be regarded as intermediate between these two. For the sake of convenience let us denote these two prominent glow conditions as condition 'A' and condition 'B'. When condition 'A' is developed the cathode is enclosed in a distinctly visible wide vapour film of randomly pulsating thickness, from which an intense golden yellow glow is emitted with Na₂SO₄ solutions. This glow pervading the whole of the cathode surface does not extend out in the wide portions of the film but appears to be confined close to the cathode surface. The intensity of hissing sound usually audible with cathode glow process is least in this condition. Another feature of this type of glow is that if the power is switched off during such glow, the vapour film does not immediately collapse but exists for a few seconds more. However, the luminescence immediately disappears on putting off the current. Of the different forms of glow, this type is the most stable situation and other forms when developed tend to switch over to this condition on their own. In fact, on the breakdown of ordinary electrolysis this type of glow is usually developed and all of our results of preceding investigations strictly apply to this situation.

When the second type, viz. the condition 'B' is developed in Na₂SO₄ solution the cathode is entirely covered with a multitude of what appear to be spark discharges (golden yellow colour). But now at the cathode there would be seen no distinct vapour film as observed under condition 'A'. The glow current and the intensity of hissing sound are considerably higher under condition 'B' than under condition 'A'. Also under condition 'B' there could be seen no transient vapour sheath at the cathode after putting off the current. The condition 'B' unlike the condition 'A' is no highly stable situation and when produced does not exist for long enough time and tends to shift to the condition 'A'.

The chemical results produced by these two different glow conditions differ considerably in their yield. But unlike acids, sodium sulphate solutions do not give rise to different types of products under these two different glow conditions. However, the novelty of the situation lies in the fact that the total as well as the non-Faradaic chemical yield is significantly less under high current glow condition (i.e., condition 'B') than under low current glow condition (i.e., condition 'A'). Further, when the nature of the cathode glow produced is intermediate between the condition 'A' and the condition 'B', the chemical effects produced are also of intermediate nature. A typical set of results showing the effect of the type of glow condition upon the chemical effects has been given in Table 2.5.

TABLE 2.5—EFFECT OF NATURE OF GLOW CONDITION ON NON-FARADAIC ASPECTS OF CATHODE GLOW

Electrolyte—1.0(N) Na₂SO₄ solution.
Electrodes :

Anode—(9.5 mm × 10 mm) Pt foil of thickness 0.05 mm in all cases.

Cathode—8 mm long Pt wire of dia. 0.35 mm in all cases.

Voltage applied (volts) D.C.	Average current during glow (mA)	Nature of glow condition produced	V _C /V _{FC} %	V _{O₂} /V _C %
224	290	Condition 'A'	302	22.3
224	445	Condition 'B'	125	6.7
224	380	Intermediate between condition 'A' and condition 'B'.	185	15.3

Thus it is seen that even in the simplest instance the chemical effects of cathode glow are greatly influenced by the nature of glow condition produced and that under the same glow condition higher the power input greater is the non-Faradaic yield.

Discussion

During cathode glow process, the cathode appears to be isolated from the electrolytic solution by being sheathed in a mantle of plasma through which current passes by some corona discharge mechanism¹. This mantle is essentially composed of electrolyte-laden water vapour plus the ions, radicals, and atoms produced by discharge through it. The idea is supported by results on spectral characteristics^{4,5} of luminescence emitted during glow-electrolysis. Current i.e., stream of electrons entering from the cathode during its transit through this discharge section collides with the water molecules therein. As a result of energy transfer following such collisions, each electron will activate or ionize several H₂O molecules as follows

These reactive species of ions and radicals produced in the mantle will then interact with one another

giving H₂, O₂, O, H₂O₂ and some H₂O back. H₂ and O₂ will be liberated in the cathode gas and H₂O₂ will enter into the body of the solution. The latter, however, will tend to get decomposed by heat of discharge and reaction with scavengers (if any).

After the act of dissociating water molecules by the processes envisaged above, the electrons (possibly hydrated) while coming out of the discharge region transfer their charges at the plasma-catholyte interface to suitable reducible species generally H₂O or H₃O⁺ to give H₂ the usual cathodic product of electrolysis in yields consistent with Faraday's law.

Viewing the glow process as above, it is thus seen that the chemical effects of cathode glow are partly non-Faradaic (arising from energy transfer processes in the discharge section) and partly Faradaic (arising from charge transfer processes at the plasma-catholyte interface). So, the gas volume liberated at the cathode should exceed the corresponding Faraday law value and contain a substantial percentage of oxygen. As shown earlier these two features are general characteristics of chemical results of cathode glow process in various aqueous systems.

In the light of this mechanism, it is expected that higher the expenditure of wattage in the glow-discharge section greater will be the non-Faradaic yield. This has been borne out in practice (see section 'Effect of some important variables on non-Faradaic aspects of galvanoluminescence').

The nature of chemical effects of both Faradaic and non-Faradaic may be substantially modified by the type of glow condition and nature of substrates present in the discharge and the possible processes giving rise to such modifications of the two general features of chemical results of cathode luminescence have already been discussed in the section 'Chemical results of cathode luminescence'.

The mechanism thus advanced in terms of activation, ionization, dissociation processes in the glow-discharge section plus charge-transfer processes at the plasma-catholyte interface can more or less explain the novelties observed in the chemical results of cathode glow process with a variety of aqueous electrolytes.

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